

Graphene Oxide/Polylactic Acid (PLA)-Based Face Mask To Combat H3N2: A Strategy Against Influenza

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Abstract

Personal protective equipment such as face masks have become a fundamental tool to fight against virus-filled airborne droplets, preventing their widespread and the appearance of pandemics. While most facemask avoid the passing of airborne particles via filtration effect, their protection effectiveness can be further increased by developing new techniques based on antiviral coatings, which can inhibit virus replication. Among different coatings, carbon-based are among the most appealing due to their low price and high antiviral properties. Most importantly, proper material selection during masks manufacturing is becoming more crucial, as the high demand and consumption of common polypropylene (PP) face mask have grown into a huge environmental hazard. Herein we present a potential face-mask system based on nanoplatelets of graphene oxide (GO) spray coated in a simple one-step procedure over a polylactic acid (PLA) textile fabric, allowing a homogeneous coating. The incorporation of GO does not affect the textile structure nor affect its air permeability while increases its water contact angle, preventing droplet trespassing. The antiviral efficiency was tested against Influenza A virus (H3N2) (strain A/Hong Kong/8/68), reaching a high reduction with no cytotoxic effect observed.

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1. Introduction

The outbreak of the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), which caused the COVID-19, has resulted close to seven million deaths as for the end of 2023¹. SARS-CoV-2 is one of the seven human CoVs (HCoVs) which have been identified. These include the three highly pathogenic CoVs, SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2, and MERS-CoV, and four CoVs with low pathogenicity, human coronavirus 229E (HCoV-229E), HCoV-OC43, HCoV-NL63, and HCoV-HKU1.² While the appearance of SARS-CoV-2 caught the world by surprise, many other pandemics generated by respiratory viruses have occurred throughout history. Remarkably, recently there have been four pandemics caused by other well-known set of viruses, influenza, in the last century (1918 (Influenza A/H1N1), 1957 (Influenza A/H2N2), 1968 (Influenza A/H3N2), 2009 (Influenza A/H1N1))³. In particular, Influenza A/H3N2 also known as the Hong Kong 1968 flu pandemic resulted in around one million deaths, globally⁴. Historical evidence shows that influenza pandemics occurred in the past century in waves between 2 to 5 years, with variable

infection and death rate. As the immunity of population grows, pandemics tend to recede⁵. Despite all the scientific information provided by researchers and studies worldwide, in 2020 the world was underprepared for the severity of the COVID-19 pandemic, which was caused by the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2. With all this information, it is clear that there are two important virus which caused some of the most severe pandemics, influenza and coronaviruses. Therefore, combined efforts are being currently aimed towards the protection of coronavirus and influenza derived pandemics⁶, from prevention towards gaining insight on how to fight against virus spread.

During this last pandemic, the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) such as face masks have become a crucial element to avoid the virus propagation mainly using surgical masks and N95 level respirators. Surgical-grade masks can effectively prevent the spread of airborne droplets, which cause the virus propagation⁷. Nonetheless, three-layer surgical masks which are composed by multiple nonwoven layers can in fact be contaminated with these droplets, letting the virus to still being able to penetrate the protective layers through spaces^{8,9}. Currently, most used face mask are composed of polypropylene (PP) or polyethylene (PE), predominately non-woven PP fabrics. Unfortunately, with such high demand comes a huge price: monthly estimated use of 129 billion face mask is disposable globally¹⁰, with the consequent huge environmental impact. Just recently, the idea of using other biodegradable materials such as polylactic acid (PLA)¹¹ have been recently explored, with key focus on their air permeability and eco-friendliness¹². Concern arises on research on the effectiveness of face masks in blocking the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 based on filtration efficiency^{11,13}, thus the choice of the fabric is fundamental¹⁴.

While the physical blocking of virus to avoid propagation has been proved a successful approach, novel functionalities are required for the next generation of face masks¹⁵. Smart face mask system offers the versatility of providing filtration efficiency, wearability among other exceptional properties that will enhance their performance^{16,17}. In fact, their utility usefulness can

be improved by providing them with superhydrophobicity, reusability, recharging or functionalization with antiviral ability¹⁸. The latter, antiviral functionalization, pretends to find suitable materials which are low cost, environmentally friendly and suitable for human use. Different antimicrobial/antiviral compounds have been proved successful such as lignin¹⁹, copper oxide²⁰ or carbon nanotubes²¹, which commonly functionalize commercial face masks or fabrics by sputtering²² or spray coating¹⁹.

Carbon based nanomaterials²³ and, in particular graphene-based nanomaterials^{24,25} are one of the main candidates to achieve higher hydrophobicity and antiviral performance. Graphene oxide (GO) has excellent physical and biological properties, widely used in antibacterial applications²⁶ and capable of capturing viruses. Ye et al.²⁷ showed that GO exhibited antiviral properties even at a low concentration (1.5 µg/mL), attributed to the negative charge and nanosheet structure, whose effectiveness was demonstrated against SARS-coV-2²⁸. Das Jana et al. showed the antiviral potential of Cu-Gr composites²⁹, while retaining high transparency. Huang et al.³⁰ showed rapid bacterial killing on a Laser-Induced Graphene (LIG) mask within 10 min. In order to find a feasible industrial application, it is necessary to find a low-cost, easy processable and rapid method to functionalize fabrics with the antiviral material, in which spray coating is a key alternative²¹. It is also important to mention that polypropylene coated with graphene masks show good endurance during test and the particles are not detached³¹, which is fundamental for their use in face mask systems.

Herein we present an advantageous approach for preparing face masks with high antiviral performance based on single-step spray coating process of GO over fabrics. Coating with GO endows the fabric surface with outstanding antiviral performance against H3N2 influenza virus, higher hydrophobicity while retaining composition and structure of the fabrics. Upon coating, no blocking of pore size or air permeability was detected, thus being suitable for respiratory

applications as face masks. The use of PLA fabrics as the bare substrate for the face mask systems awards the GO@PLA face mask as an alternative for conventional PP face masks, which suppose a current environmental and recycling challenge.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Materials

Graphene oxide (GO) dispersion in water was purchased from (Grupo Antolín). Further dispersions were prepared by diluting the as-purchased suspension with distilled water. The optimal concentration used was 3800 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ²⁷, whose particle size is shown in **Figure S1**. Polylactic acid (PLA) fabrics were cut into long straps of (50 cm width) to which the spray coating was performing. Afterwards, coated samples were cut into smaller size for testing.

2.2 Fabrication of the coated GO@PLA fabrics

The desired size of the fabric was cut in a clean environment with the aid of a cutter knife. Then, it was placed over filter paper and positioned with the use of tape. The samples were first cleaned with a spray of N_2 gas. Spray coating was performed with a spray gun from Sagola 474. Constant pressure was applied with pressured air. The spray gun was positioned on the normal respective to the fabric at 15 cm of height, as recommended by the manufacturer. Coatings were prepared by passing only once over the sample, unless stated otherwise.

2.3 Characterization of the coated GO@PLA fabrics

Samples micrographs were obtained using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) instrument (Apreo 2S low vacuum) working at 0.5 mbar and 5 kV. The Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra were measured in ATR mode with a thermofisher Nicolet 5700 spectrometer. Raman spectra were obtained by Renishaw inVia microRaman spectrometer with a

laser of 532 nm wavelength, at 10s exposure and 5% laser power used. The magnification of x50 was used, which was equivalent to a spot size of $\sim 1.5 \mu\text{m}$.

Conventional DSC and temperature modulated DSC (TMDSC) were performed on the uncoated fabric and after coating with GO using a TA Instruments model Q25. For the conventional DSC, the samples (10 mg) were held isothermally for 5min and heated to 190°C at 10°C /min to determine the cold crystallization temperature (T_{cc}), glass transition temperature (T_g) and nominal melting temperature (T_{melt}). For the TMDSC, the samples were held for 5 min, and standard heating ramp of 3°C/min was chosen, a modulation period of 60 s and a modulation temperature amplitude of 1°C was chosen based upon the recommended specifications. A N_2 purge was used for all experiments. Baseline calibration was performed regularly with empty pans at 3 and 10°C/min, and a four-point temperature calibration was performed with Indium as metal standards. Careful baseline calibration is crucial for polymers exhibiting broad and weak transitions. The cell constant was calculated by standard analysis of an Indium standard, the heat capacity calibration constant for the modulation calibration was done using a standard sapphire sample.

Thickness have been measured using a DUALSCOPE® MP0 Coating Thickness Gauge of Fischer Instrumentation by Eddy current method with an accuracy of $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$. Each fabric was measured 40 times along a 200 cm^2 sample. In the case of the original, untreated sample, the set of 40 measurements was carried out twice, completely independently, to check the reproducibility of the results.

Permeability to air has been measured using a porometer II from Coulter. The permeability test applies a static pressure difference and assesses airflow through the system. Reference no-coated sample permeability has been measured twice, before and after the GO-coated sample, in

all cases using pressure differences between 0.1 and 0.3 bar; air permeability through each sample was measured for at least four pressures, repeating the measurement at each pressure 5 times.

Pore size has been evaluated using a gas-liquid displacement method using the same porometer II equipment, in this case using the pore size analysis mode (as described at ³²). In this mode, the continuous flow versus pressure dependence for two runs, first “wet” and secondly “dry”, of the same sample allows to know the distribution of pore sizes. In this case this procedure was performed using 3M™ Fluorinet™ Electronic Liquid FC-43 as wetting liquid. This liquid is used because it is inert and has low surface tension, to which, as usual, zero contact angle has been assigned.

The wetting contact angle of the non-treated and of the coated surfaces was determined by the sessile drop method with water using a goniometer (Tamé-Har 200 mod. p/n 200-F1, Syuccasunna, NJ, USA).

2.4 Antiviral efficiency

All testing procedures and the results were performed and reported according to ISO standard 18184:2019 “Textiles — Determination of antiviral activity of textile products” ³³ which was obtained from the “Instituto Valenciano de Microbiología” (IVAMI, Spain), test which is accredited by the National Accreditation and Certification Entity (ENAC, Spain).

3. Results and Discussion

In this work we explore a practical method to produce facemask based on PLA coated with graphene oxide (GO). This process, illustrated in **Figure 1**, includes initially dispersing the GO solution in water in the desired concentration, which in this work was fixed to 3.8 mg/mL as explained in the previous section. Ye et al. ²⁷ showed that GO solution possess high antiviral efficiency down to a concentration of 1.5 µg/mL, while other authors point towards higher contents

(50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)³⁴. It is expected that fibers need higher content to show similar antiviral efficiency as in vitro testing, as the area of virus contact is smaller in the fabric. Then, the solution is added to the spray coating gun and sprayed constant distance and speed, being all the process performed at a fume hood for safety and cleanliness of the samples. Finally, the coated sample is left to dry inside the fume hood and then cut into different sizes, depending on the application. It can be observed that, by optical inspection of the samples (presented in **Figure S2** and **Figure 2(a)**), the coating is clearly present due to its characteristic greyish color. Also in **Figure S2** it can be observed how this method can be employed repeatedly to obtain thicker coatings. It is important to mention that this coating is intended for the outer layer or the middle layer of a common 3-ply face mask system, allowing further protection if GO is detached from the surface. Some testing about the stability of the GO coating is shown in **Figure S3**.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the methodology developed for coating PLA fabrics with the GO solution.

3.1 Morphology and compositional characterization of the modified GO@PLA fabrics.

Several characterization techniques were employed to study the GO-coating effect over the fabrics. As observed in **Figure 2(a)**, after coating PLA fabric presents a greyish color as opposed to the white color of the PLA fabric. SEM micrographs were employed to observe the morphology of the coated fabrics. At low magnification we can observe the microstructure of the PLA fabric (**Figure 2(b)**), composed by several fibers of micrometric size (**Figure 2(c)**) arbitrarily distributed

through the sample. Analysis of the energy- dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) spectra is presented in **Figure 2(d)**. Due to the fibers being extremely sensitive to the electron beam, to obtain EDS spectra low vacuum conditions were employed with small voltage and intensity. The EDS spectra indicates the presence of the main components of the fabrics, mostly C and O.

GO-coated sample is presented in **Figure 2(e)** and **Figure 2(f)**, which despite being obtained under the same conditions as the uncoated sample different behavior is observed under the electron beam which affects more the GO coated samples. As observed in the EDS spectra (**Figure 2(g)**), no significant differences are observed among coated and uncoated sample mostly due to the limitations of this technique for the detection of light elements. At higher magnification with the same voltage the fibers are charged and thus, damaged, due to the SEM electron beam. Nonetheless is clearly observed that the samples covered by GO are more damaged, probably due poor electron conductivity. The EDS mapping of the GO-coated sample is depicted in **Figure S4**, showing the homogeneous distribution of the coating. Nonetheless it should be mentioned that this technique does not allow to differentiate the coating content from the fabric, both with high C and O contents.

Despite the clear presence of graphene oxide due to the color change (**Figure 2(h)**), further analysis was employed to assure its presence and influence over the fabric. Raman spectra is presented in **Figure 2(i)** where spectra obtained in the point marked in the inset clearly shows the presence of GO. The uncoated PLA sample presents several Raman modes, such as those at 2998 and 2947 and 2881 cm^{-1} (attributed to the asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching vibrations of the C–H bond), an intense band at 1757 cm^{-1} (attributed to the stretching vibrations of the C=O bond), the band at 1448 cm^{-1} (due to deformation vibration of the CH_3 group), the bands at 1126 cm^{-1} and 1089 cm^{-1} (assigned to the C–O–C binding vibrations), and the band at 870 cm^{-1} (vibrations of the C–COO bond)³⁵. The GO-coated sample presents similar Raman

modes at close positions, moreover it clearly presents two very strong modes at $\sim 1347\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1588\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are deconvoluted in **Figure 2(i)**. These modes are attributed to the D and G-band, whose origin is due to disorder-induced sp^3 hybridized carbon and due to first-order Raman-allowed tangential sp^2 hybridized carbons, respectively ^{36,37}, attributed to the GO presence. In the inset image, a mode at 1757 cm^{-1} from PLA can be also clearly observed. 2D Raman mapping is present in **Figure S5** where the intensity of the ID is depicted and clearly it can be observed that it is homogeneously distributed. The presence of areas with higher intensity is also related with the difference of height of the fibers where the mapping has been recorded.

FTIR spectra of the uncoated fabric and GO-coated sample are presented in **Figure 2(j)**. PLA fabric shows the main expected modes for this material³⁸, being some of the most remarkable C-O at 1130 cm^{-1} , C-O-C at 1185 cm^{-1} , C=O at 1754 cm^{-1} and C-H at 2997 cm^{-1} . The GO coated sample presents similar vibrational modes as the uncoated sample, probably the most representative change among both spectrum is the fact that the modes at 2997 and 3500 cm^{-1} are remarkably higher in the case of GO coated, which could be attributed to O-H groups from GO. Finally, coated and GO-coated samples were analyzed by means of XPS, whose discussion can be found in **Figure S6**.

Figure 2: (a) Photos of the uncoated fabric and coated fabric, shaped into a facemask (b) SEM micrograph of the uncoated fabric (c) zoomed region of the fabrics and (d) its corresponding EDS (e) SEM micrographs of the GO-coated fabric (f) zoomed region of the fabrics and (g) its corresponding EDS spectra (h) schematic representation of the coating process (i) Raman spectrum. Inset shows optical and (j) FTIR spectrum.

3.2 Thermal properties

PLA masks have been characterized by DSC in order to know which thermal phenomena occur and at what temperature they occur, the structural state, and the changes generated by adding GO on the PLA of the mask. This is important because its crystallinity and T_g can affect the performance of the mask.³⁹ In the supplementary material the results obtained by conventional DSC (**Figures S7- S8**) are presented, which are further complemented in this section, while **Figure S9** shows the analysis of the TMDSC.

The Modulated results for the PLA mask are shown in **Figure 3(a)**. The Reversing Heat Flow (Heat Capacity Component) shows a slight T_g around 55°C, different from the clear T_g seen

in the DSC standard around 60°C. This has its origin in two causes, the first is that the sample having such a high percentage of crystallinity masks the T_g in the reversible part, and the second is that, as observed in the non-reversing heat part (Kinetic component), there is a two-stage enthalpic relaxation/recovery, which does contribute to the total heat curve. The fact that the T_g is higher is due to the fact that the sweep velocity is three times lower than that used in conventional DSC. This was probably caused by the fast-heating rate induced superheating, which was attributed to low heat conduction of polymer.⁴⁰

Figure 3. (a) TMDSC results on a sample taken from PLA mask and (b) GO coated mask. Reversible (blue), non-reversible (green) and total heat flow (red) data are shown. Each of the flows has been normalized and contains with the same colors the results associated with the graphical calculation of T_g, T_{ap}, T_m and crystallinity.

In addition, two melting peaks (T_{m1} and T_{m2}) are observed in the reversible part. In the case of PLA these peaks correspond to 156°C and 163°C respectively (**Figure 3**). Double or multiple melting behaviors is often found on many semi-crystalline polymers upon heating in scanning calorimetry^{41,42}. T_{m1} is attributed to the melting of original crystals formed before the DSC scan, and the T_{m2} is associated with the melting of the recrystallized components during heating scan⁴³. The recrystallization occurring during the sweep is proportional to the crystallinity

linked to the first endothermic peak⁴⁴, in both cases representing approximately 1.25% of the total crystallinity, confirming a correct measurement by MDSC. After melting in the reversible part, a slight crystallization peak can be observed in **Figure 3(a)**.

The Reversing and Non-Reversing Heat Flow Curves are integrated using a linear integration line. The limits of integration range from a temperature before the pre-melting of imperfect crystals begins through a temperature above the melt peak. In this case, the integrated area of the Reversing Heat Flow is 14.25 J/g, and the area in the Non-Reversing Heat Flow is 33.45 J/g, which suggests there exists some concentration of crystallinity that would equate to 47.7 J/g of energy in the melt of the uncoated sample. This means that the crystallinity of the material is around 48%, which represents 4% with respect to that observed by conventional DSC. Due to its high crystallinity, it can be affirmed that the PLA analyzed was subjected to isothermally annealing, which implies a semi-crystalline structure and melting behavior⁴⁵

It is important to highlight that the non-reversing endothermic signal is typically due to complete melting of separate lamellae or stacks of lamellae⁴⁶ and reversing endothermic signal is due to partial melting of lamellae⁴⁷. Also, the non-reversible endotherm in the final melting region occurs at a slightly higher temperature than the reversible endotherm, as is typical. The existence of endothermic peaks in both the non-reversible and reversible parts has been observed in semi-crystalline polymer systems with high relative crystallinity⁴⁸.

Figure 3(b) shows the result of the MDSC performed on the sample extracted from the GO-coated PLA mask. In this case the T_g is still weakly displayed at around 55°C. If we look at the pre-melt peak (T_{ap}), located in the non-reversible component, we observe that the presence of GO has extended its amplitude and has shifted its maximum by about 1.5°C. On the other hand, the peaks T_{m1} and T_{m2} maintain their position, and only the enthalpy of the non-reversible part

varies slightly. The crystallinity of the material is approximately 47%. The above results show that neither the deposition method, nor the GO employed, produce minimal changes in the thermal phenomena of interest (T_g , T_m) or in the structural state of PLA mask.

3.3 Porosity, permeability and wettability

To ensure the validity of the coated fabrics for use in a face mask scenario, it is necessary to test different parameters related with breathability and porosity of the samples. As in this case a starting support has been coated with GO, it is necessary to check if characteristics as the pore size and permeability of the samples are preserved after the coating. We have characterized the samples through some of their relevant physical characteristics for this purpose. Of all the possible ones, it is considered that the most relevant are two geometric parameters, such as thickness and pore size, and two properties that account for its functionality, such as permeability and wettability.

Figure 4: (a) Thickness of the sample (× symbols represent minimum and maximum value; black dash is mean value and gray zone corresponds to standard deviation) (b) Permeability of no-coated and GO-coated samples (c) Resistance to airflow of no-sample, no-coated and, GO-coated. and (d) Pore size distribution for no-coated (black) and GO-coated (red) samples (e) Contact angle measurements of a 5 μL water droplet as a function of time at room temperature conditions.

The thickness of the coated and uncoated masks is presented in **Figure 4(a)**, where mean (\pm standard deviation), minimum and maximum values are presented. As shown, the thickness of uncoated sample is 45 ± 15 μm, with minimum and maximum values between 20 and 80 μm. The coating with GO causes average sample thickness to increase by 25 μm. The minimum thickness barely increases from 20 to 28 μm, and at the maximum value it goes from the 85 of the sample without coating to a slightly higher 120 μm in the case of the coated sample. This small variation in thickness do not imply variations in air permeability at all, as shown in **Figure 4(b)**.

The resistance to air flow, determined as the slope of the plot of Δp against permeability, can be considered as the sum of contribution of all elements placed in series. After subtracting the resistance offered by the holder, all samples present a very similar resistance. The high permeability of any of the samples makes a very small contribution to the minimum intrinsic resistance of the measuring equipment. Although we are close to the sensitivity limit of the equipment the values are representative enough to conclude that resistances do not show a significantly higher value due to the fact that they have a GO coating. The resistance contribution added by the GO coating to the original sample is totally negligible, $0.0164 \pm 0.005 \text{ bar cm}^2 \text{ L} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ versus 0.0163 ± 0.004 and $0.165 \pm 0.005 \text{ bar cm}^2 \text{ L} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ of the original textile, graphically represented in **Figure 4(c)**. The practical repercussion that the coating could present in terms of loss of flow or permeability is shown to be equivalently negligible in the **Figure 4(c)**. Flow or permeability have a maximum decay of 1.9% in comparison with uncoated sample. It can be considered that the application of GO coating does not have a negative impact on the permeability of the product to air flow, which allows it to continue to be used in suitable conditions for breathing. The air flow takes place through all the pores that connect both sides of the material. To achieve adequate retention by steric effects, the maximum pore size must be small enough. Influenza virus particles have a size of 80–120 nm⁴⁹, often propagated in droplets of around 20 μm size⁵⁰.

Results concerning the initial pore distribution are shown in **Figure 4(d)**. For the uncoated fabric is in the range from 10 to 50 μm . After the GO-coating process, the pore distribution results were as expected. The total number was not expected to undergo a representative variation, only some of the smallest could have been closed, totally irrelevant in the distribution presented by the sample. The slight increase observed in the values of resistance to air flow is perfectly justified by observing a shift, also very slight, towards smaller pore size values. The expected effect of the

coating on the support is a reduction in the size of all the pores. Evaluating it only in the largest pores, the effect of GO-coating can be estimated in a cover of about 5 μm , producing a decrease in pore diameter of 10 μm . These results are fully consistent with the total increase in thickness measured directly (**Figure 4(a)**).

Filter efficiency is a fundamental parameter for commercial masks. As mentioned, droplets contain the perfect media for viruses, especially dangerous are the droplets under 5 μm . Pore size distribution for the uncoated and coated sample is within the same range, thus it can be concluded that after the coating the pore size and porosity of the samples is preserved even after coating. It is known that viruses spread via airborne saliva droplets, thus, the hydrophobicity of face mask is one of the main factors for filtering and inhibiting the intrusion of viruses⁵¹. The surface wetting of the samples has been studied by static and dynamic contact angle (**Figure 4(e)**) by comparing GO-coated and uncoated fabrics employing equal size of 2 cm x 2 cm squares. Water droplets were dropped at a specific height using the water contact angle equipment. Bare substrates present a negligible contact angle, as the drop is almost instantly adsorbed by the PLA fabric. GO coated sample presents a higher contact angle (varies from 90.1° to 71.0° in 5 min). GO coatings can show both hydrophilic and hydrophobic behavior, depending on several conditions⁵²⁻⁵⁴. In our case a higher contact angle as compared with the pristine fabric the outside⁵⁵.

3.4 Antiviral properties of the masks

There are different methods to test the antiviral surfaces^{33,56}, as explained by various authors⁵⁷, nonetheless for porous substrates as the PLA fabrics employed in this work, ISO 18184:2019 is one of the most used.

The antiviral efficiency of the coated samples was tested following ISO standard 18184:2019 “Textiles -Determination of antiviral activity of textile products”³³ performed at the

IVAMI institution (Instituto Valenciano de Microbiología), assay accredited by ENAC (Spanish National Accreditation Body) ISO 17025. The main steps concerning this test are shown in **Figure 5(a)** while the main results are summarized in **Figure S10**. Following the standard, the titration method is based on TCID50 (Tissue Culture Infective Dose 50%). In this case the chosen virus was Influenza A virus (H3N2) A/Hong Kong/8/68/ (ATCC VR-1679). The assay incubation temperature was $35\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the virus detection method was the cytopathic effect. Contact time was 24h at $25\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ after which to stop product activity a dilution in ice cold medium was used. Cytotoxicity remained within safe range lower than one logarithmic scale as shown in **Figure S5**.

According to ISO 18184:2019 the antiviral activity [Mv] is described by the to the reduction of the logarithm of the average value of the three values of the infectious titer of the non-treated samples immediately after inoculation and the average of the logarithm of the three values of the infectivity titer after the contact time. To calculate Mv, the following formula is applied:

$$[Mv] = \log Va - \log Vc \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

where Va is the average of the logarithm of the 3 values of the infectivity titer immediately after the inoculation of the non-treated samples, and Vc is the average of the logarithm of the 3 infectivity titer values after the contact time with the treated fabric samples. An antiviral activity value [Mv] equal to or greater than 3 indicates that the test product shows excellent antiviral effect while an antiviral activity value between 2 and 3, ($2 \leq [Mv] < 3$) indicates that the test product shows a good antiviral effect. The reduction percentage is obtained from the formula:

$$(1 - 10^{-[Mv]}) \cdot 100 \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

Figure 5: (a) Summary of the main steps on the ISO standard 18184:2019 “Textiles - Determination of antiviral activity of textile products” (b) results of the test against H3N2 (strain A/Hong Kong/8/68) virus in contact with after 24h of exposure and (c) percentage reduction of viruses after exposure time (d) schematic representation of the supposed mechanism of virus capture and inhibition.

According to our results (**Figure 5 (b)**), viral quantification and antiviral activity (M_v) with the 95% confidence is 2.55 ± 0.55 TCID₅₀ and thus, corresponds (**Equation 2**) to a reduction percentage of 99.72% (**Figure 5 (c)**), against Influenza A virus (H3N2) with respect to the control samples immediate after inoculation. As the antiviral activity value (M_v) is greater than 2, according to the ISO standard, the product shows a good antiviral effect.

The antibacterial/antiviral behavior of Graphene oxide has been previously reported²⁶ and the main advances are summarized in **Table 1**. Recently with the appearance of the COVID-19 pandemic, their application as antivirals has broadly increased. Ye et al. ²⁷ showed that GO can exhibit significant antiviral properties even at a low concentration (1.5 µg/mL) due to GO may be attributed to the negative charge and nanosheet structure, further demonstrated for SARS-coV-2 variants by other authors²⁸. Das Jana et al demonstrated the potential of Cu-Gr²⁹ composites, with high transparency, which could be used in a variety of transparent composites. The use of

graphene-systems in face mask systems has also been recently studied. As mentioned on the introduction, the current approaches for improved face mask respiratory systems mainly cover superhydrophobicity, superior filtration efficiency or antiviral. For example, the use of graphene nanosheet-embedded carbon (GNEC) film has shown a superior filtration efficiency and high hydrophobicity³⁶, which also was reported for laser induced graphene⁵⁸. Antiviral efficacy of GO has been tested in suspension^{27,28} while its study over masks and in particular, over PLA masks, has not been reported per authors knowledge. Regarding the action mechanism of virus protection, several steps might be involved which are schematized in **Figure 5(d)**. On one hand, the GO-coating endows the PLA fabric with higher hydrophobicity, thus blocking water droplets containing virus to pass through the fiber media. Also, the fibrous filtering does not allow the pass of droplets size higher than the pore size shown in **Figure 5(d)** which is lower with the GO coating. Mechanism of GO inhibition of viruses is more complex and remains to be elucidated^{27,59}. It has been reported that GO inactivates the virus even before it enters the cell. In the case of pseudorabies virus (PRV, a DNA virus) GO was observed to inhibit the virus infection by direct interaction between the GO and the virus by the sharp-edged structure of GO. Also, the negative charge of GO favors its interaction with the positively charged virus, thus attracting the virus via electrostatic interaction. GO could interact with the viral particles and destroy their structures which leads to the disruption of the viral function and thus prevents its replication. Recently²⁸ SARS-CoV-2 was attributed to be adsorbed the GO surface followed by its inactivation through decomposition of spike protein on the surface of GO, disruption the virus cycle. The fact that GO-coated surfaces can absorb molecules via the pi-stacking interacting and hydrogen bonding is one of the key reason why it can be employed for detection of influenza subtype viral genes⁶⁰. The inactivation of H3N2 virus mediated by GO could be therefore attributed to the virus capture due to the negative charge and functional groups of GO, which then inactivates the virus via the direct interaction of the GO

layers and the H3N2, destroying their surface proteins and extracting the RNA, as has been observed for H9N2 virus³⁴. Nonetheless it is worth mentioning that for the latter case, there was a strong dependence of the temperature, reaching only around 1 log scale at 37°C while in this case we observe a higher logarithmic decrease even at lower assay temperature.

Table 1: Comparison with other carbon-based systems in the literature.

Graphene-based system	Antibacterial	Antiviral efficiency	Virus	%Reduction	Year	Reference
Continuous wave (CW) laser-induced forward transfer (LIFT) showed		Not tested	-	-	2020	⁵⁵
Reusable Sterilization Masks Based on Electrothermal Graphene Filters	Self-Escherichia coli (E. coli)	-	-	99.8%	2020	⁶¹
Laser-induced graphene (LIG)		Tested against bacteria	-	-	2020	⁵⁸
Graphene nanosheet-embedded carbon (GNEC) film		Not tested. Tested filtration efficiency	-		2020	³⁶
Graphene suspension		Tested	SARS-CoV-2 strains	for 1 and 60 min	2021	²⁸
Graphene nanoplatelet and graphene oxide @cotton fabrics		Tested	SARS-CoV-2	79% in 2h	2021	⁶²
RGO/Ag/Cu nps	Staphylococcus aureus by 78-99%	-	-	-	2021	⁶³

GO/AgNP	zone of inhibition (ZOI) of 19 and 18 mm against the bacterial strains such as S.aureus and E. coli.				-	2021	64
Graphene oxide suspension		Tested	Pseudorabies virus (PRV)			2022	27
Graphene Oxide/Fe ₃ O ₄ /Chitosan		Not tested	-	-		2022	65
Graphene oxide		Tested	SARS-CoV-2	-		2023	66
Graphene oxide embedded polyvinylidene fluoride nanofiber		Not tested	-	-		2023	67
Spray-coated graphene oxide @PLA fabrics (GO@PLA)		Tested	H3N2 Influenza A virus	99.72% in 24h		2023	This work

4. Conclusions

In the present study, we have demonstrated the antiviral efficiency against virus Influenza A virus (H3N2) (strain A/Hong Kong/8/68) virus of PLA fabrics coated with graphene oxide (GO). The use of PLA fabrics presents an alternative to conventional face masks based in meltblown polypropylene. To achieve GO@PLA, firstly PLA fabrics can be coated with GO via a single-step and scalable method with the use of spray coating, assuring a well-distribution over the fabrics. GO modifies the textile wettability, while retaining pore size and permeability of the samples, allowing air flow and breathability of the samples while preventing droplet absorption offering

better protection from incoming virus within the respiratory droplets. Finally, the antiviral efficiency was tested against a representative influenza virus, H3N2, showing a high antiviral efficiency. These results support the use of GO-based coating which could enhance the inhibition of an influenza-type virus, retaining the fabric properties while increasing its hydrophobicity and antiviral activity.

Supporting Information

Fig S1:GO particle size analysis; Fig S2: Optical images of the uncoated and GO-coated samples; Fig S3: Tape test GO-coated samples; Fig S4: EDS mapping of the GO-coated samples; Fig S5: Raman mapping GO-coated samples; Fig S6: XPS survey of the samples and C 1s core level; Fig S7: Conventional DSC of the uncoated sample; Fig S8: Conventional DSC of the GO-coated sample; Fig S9: TMDSC of the coated and uncoated samples; Fig S10: Summary of the results of the ISO 18184:2019 assay.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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